

Review

CROP MODELLING APPLIED TO PORTUGUESE VITICULTURE: A BRIEF OVERVIEW

MODELAÇÃO DE CULTURAS APLICADA À VITICULTURA PORTUGUESA: UMA VISÃO GERAL

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SUMMARY

Traditional viticulture is becoming increasingly insufficient to deal with the pressure from climate changes and market competitiveness. Due to these challenges, efficient modelling is needed to increase the efficiency and modernization of the sector. This work presents a review of the most relevant research on grapevine crop modelling, including an assessment of statistical and dynamic modelling, as well as machine learning techniques and applications. A brief overview of the viticultural sector (national and international) is given, highlighting the declining vineyard areas and economic fragmentation, particularly in Portugal. Drawing from agricultural systems science, recent studies on climate change effects on European viticulture, and advancements in dynamic and machine learning models, the research aims to address the complexities of vineyard management and climate change. The importance of crop models in viticulture is evidenced, and opportunities for future improvements are presented, such as enhanced phenological modelling and precision viticulture techniques. Challenges, including data quality issues and the need for region-specific models, are also identified. The resulting impact of overcoming these challenges can have a very significant influence on the long-term efficiency, productivity, resilience and sustainability of the Portuguese wine industry. The review concludes that the future of viticulture will rely on integrating advanced modelling techniques with traditional practices, emphasizing the need for interdisciplinary collaboration and real-time data processing to ensure adaptability in an uncertain climate.

RESUMO

A viticultura tradicional está a tornar-se cada vez mais insuficiente para lidar com a pressão das alterações climáticas e da competitividade do mercado. Devido a estes desafios, é necessária uma modelação eficiente para aumentar a eficiência e a modernização do setor. Este trabalho apresenta uma revisão da investigação mais relevante sobre modelação de culturas de videira, incluindo uma avaliação da modelação estática e dinâmica, bem como técnicas e aplicações de aprendizagem automática. É apresentada uma breve visão geral do setor vitivinícola (nacional e internacional), destacando a diminuição das áreas de vinha e a fragmentação económica, particularmente em Portugal. Baseando-se na ciência dos sistemas agrícolas, em estudos recentes sobre os efeitos das alterações climáticas na viticultura europeia e nos avanços em modelos dinâmicos e de aprendizagem automática, a investigação visa abordar as complexidades da gestão das vinhas e das alterações climáticas. A importância dos modelos de culturas na viticultura é evidenciada, e são apresentadas oportunidades para melhorias futuras, como o aperfeiçoamento da modelação fenológica e técnicas de viticultura de precisão. São também identificados desafios, incluindo questões de qualidade dos dados e a necessidade de modelos específicos para cada região. O impacto resultante da superação destes desafios pode ter uma influência muito significativa na eficiência, produtividade, resiliência e sustentabilidade a longo prazo da indústria vitivinícola portuguesa. A revisão conclui que o futuro da viticultura dependerá da integração de técnicas de modelação avançadas com práticas tradicionais, enfatizando a necessidade de colaboração interdisciplinar e processamento de dados em tempo real para garantir a adaptabilidade num clima incerto.

Keywords: Viticulture, dynamic models, statistical models, machine learning, climate change.

Palavras-chave: Viticultura, modelos dinâmicos, modelos estatísticos, aprendizagem automática, alterações climáticas.

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INTRODUCTION

In the latest FAOSTAT (2023) report available it is shown that in 2022, the global agricultural land area amounted to 4,781 million hectares, which represents over one-third of the total land area worldwide.

The total area of cropland within agricultural land is 1,573 million hectares, while the area of permanent meadows and pastures is 3,208 million hectares. The evolution from 2000 to 2022 is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Evolution of the normalized agricultural production values (2000-2022) for the World, Europe and Portugal from FAOSTAT.

From the cropland-covered area, about 7,2 million ha, the area under vineyards represents 0,45% of the cropland or 0,15% of total agricultural land (OIV, 2024).

According to FAO statistics, the global agricultural sector has seen significant fluctuations in value, with the total value of world agriculture estimated at approximately USD 3.5 trillion in 2022, reflecting a steady increase from around USD 2.5 trillion in 2000 (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2022). These trends have been followed by Europe and Portugal, as

evidenced by Figure 2, which illustrates the evolution of agricultural value (normalized values) from 2000 to 2023. Since the 1950's the world's population has almost doubled, and it's expected to keep increasing until 2100 capping off at about 10.4 billion people (United Nations, 2024). Evolution of land area value per hectare, as illustrated in Figure 3, increased at about 60% (in USD). In the present scenario, it is evident the increased scarcity of agricultural land in contrast with increased population.

Figure 2. Evolution of the percentage of permanent meadows and cropland in world agricultural land (2000-2022). On the principal axis agricultural land in billion hectares, on the secondary axis the percentage of cropland and permanent.

Figure 3. Evolution of the value per hectare of agricultural land (2000-2022). USD_PPP/ha - (Power Purchasing Parity in United States Dollar per hectare).

Moreover, climate change and reduction in agricultural land, about 86 million ha since 2000 (FAOSTAT, 2023), has also had a considerable impact in some areas. Being that arable land is a (virtually) non-expanding resource, there is a need to manage these lands efficiently (Fraga *et al.*, 2012; FAOSTAT, 2020).

As the global population grows, the need to sustainably maintain the current farmland is highlighted and can be aided through

understanding which, in turn, requires monitoring, measuring, and analysis of the physical aspects of these ecosystems (Ferro and Catania, 2023).

Viticulture, the cultivation of grapevines, is deeply intertwined with climate sensitivity and the impacts of climate change, being reliant on adaptive strategies to ensure the continued production of quality wines is economically sustainable (Rességuier *et al.*, 2020).

This sensitivity underscores the importance of monitoring grapevine responses to climate variations, as these responses can provide valuable insights into broader ecological changes (Santos *et al.*, 2020a). Such is the connection between the grapevine and the climate that, it has been claimed, grapevines serve as a barometer for historical and contemporary climate variations, highlighting their sensitivity to climatic shifts, particularly in phenology—where plant responses can be easily seen in phenological events such as the timing of flowering and véraison. Studies have shown that changes in temperature, which mainly point to an increase in global temperature, can lead to earlier phenological dates, which can impact the overall quality of the wine produced (Mosedale *et al.*, 2016).

Historical records (Hansen *et al.*, 2020), since 1880, point that the last decade has the 10 hottest years globally, and more recently, 2024 was officially declared the hottest so far. Being that agriculture and viticulture are vulnerable to climate change these impacts are already being felt by producers worldwide.

Early prediction and monitoring of viticultural parameters, such as phenology, water status, yield, and potential wine characteristics, are crucial for Portugal's winemaking sector (Fraga *et al.*, 2017). Accurate forecasts allow for timely vineyard operations and interventions, particularly regarding pest and disease management, while long-term projections give the producer the chance to improve soil and canopy management, contributing to a more reliable strategic planning (Ferreira *et al.*, 2020).

Agriculture, and consequently viticulture, needs a considerable investment of time and labour, particularly when implementing sustainable management practices (Mosedale *et al.*, 2015; Santos *et al.*, 2020b). This is particularly evidenced in the current situation regarding climate change impacts which can potentially decrease production (Venios *et al.*,

2020). The International Organisation of Vine and Wine (OIV, 2024) has pointed to 2023 as the lowest annual production in the last 60 years, together with the aggravation of world vineyard surface area reduction in the last few decades, as evidenced by the latest data.

In 2023, the worldwide wine export value reached 36.0 billion EUR, marking the second-highest level ever documented, albeit seeing a 4.7% decline compared to 2022. The significant growth in the average export price to 3.62 EUR/L, which is 29% more than the average for 2020, can be mainly ascribed to increased expenses borne by producers, importers, and intermediaries (OIV, 2024).

The United Nations 21st Conference of the Parties in Paris in 2015 emphasized the need for a Special Report on climate change mitigation efforts. In this sequence, assessments of agriculture's greenhouse gas emissions and food security impacts are essential and are deemed a priority (Antle *et al.*, 2017). Currently, efforts are underway to assess changes in crop productivity and safety, developing adaptation and mitigation strategies for climate change. It is uncertain how greenhouse gas emissions will change in future, so, climate change studies cover different Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) – for example SSP1, SSP3, and SSP5. These pathways provide frameworks for analysing potential future socioeconomic conditions resulting in different climate change scenarios, with emerging studies in this area within the European Union (Ding *et al.*, 2018; Kovács *et al.*, 2018; Sirmik *et al.*, 2018; Santos *et al.*, 2020a; Bucur and Dejeu 2022; Nesbitt *et al.*, 2022; Xiao and Shi 2023). It is also expected that the relevance of regulatory entities in the sector will increase, while supporting producers in the face of mitigation and adaptation actions to climate change (Gil, 2021). Currently, the situation in Portugal mimics the world's trends with a decrease in land area used for vineyards, as evidenced by Figure 4.

Figure 4. Evolution of vineyard area in Portugal, from 1989 to 2023 (thousand ha). Source: Authors adaptation, source data from IVV, accessed July 2024.

Duarte *et al.* (2022) point out that the economic aspect is also an aggravating factor in the Portuguese wine industry, as most of the companies are micro companies (about 2600) and only five are considered large companies. For this study, the authors considered a large company if it had a business volume greater than 50 million euros, and a micro company if it had a business value below 2 million euros. Large and micro companies hold sensibly the same business volume of 20% and reflect a fiercely competitive market for new players. Duarte *et al.* (2022) also mentioned that more than 90% of the companies in the Portuguese sector have a sole owner, and 95% of them have the owner as the only labour force, constituting 40% of the business volume. This fractioning of the market also hinders the communication and the implementation of efficient decision support systems.

All these factors contribute to the somewhat frail reality of viticultural endeavours, highlighting the fact that precision viticulture is increasingly becoming important for addressing challenges, including productivity, environmental impact, food security, and sustainability (Kamilaris and Prenafeta-Boldú, 2018).

Advanced modelling techniques are becoming crucial for the viticulture sector to adapt to

climate change's impact on grape production and quality. These models optimize vineyard management, enhance yield, and ensure sustainability (Biasi *et al.*, 2019). This study explores crop modelling in Portuguese viticulture, assessing its potential to improve decision-making, promote resilience, and contribute to environmental sustainability and economic viability. This methodology was chosen to comprehensively synthesize existing knowledge, identify opportunities and gaps in this sector, and provide a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

METHODOLOGY

The literature review focuses on crop models in viticulture, particularly those incorporating Machine Learning (ML) techniques in Portuguese viticulture. The process began with the selection of keywords, which were grouped into three categories based on their relevance. The Web of Science database was chosen for its accessibility. The identification of query keywords was grouped into three categories as shown in Figure 5, selected arbitrarily by relevance, and considered as a first set. The dataset from Web of Science was selected, due to easy access and followed by the screening method which entails applying exclusion criteria to publications based on keywords.

Figure 5. Search keywords divided into the three chosen categories.

The results from the advanced query from Web of Science were exported and analyzed using Python code (Rossum, 2007) to count keyword occurrences from 2004 to 2023. The selected keywords were based on two specific criteria: 1) the keyword appeared in at least three articles and, 2) the keyword matched a keyword from the initial set. These criteria ensured consistent usage in the literature, which concludes there is continuous relevance of the topic. Articles not meeting these criteria were excluded from further analysis. This process effectively narrowed down the number of studies for in-depth evaluation, focusing on the most relevant research. The final step involved a careful manual review of the remaining publications, examining titles and abstracts. Finally, the selected articles were reviewed as results. This systematic approach (Webster and Watson, 2002) ensures a comprehensive evaluation of the literature on ML applications in viticulture crop models. It helps identify the most relevant and current research topics, providing a solid foundation for further study in this field.

DISCUSSION

The integration of ML in viticulture offers promising opportunities and can contribute to the advancement of precision viticulture and sustainable grape production practices (Liakos *et al.*, 2018; Kasimati *et al.*, 2021; Alibabaei *et al.*, 2022).

The query results for the database selected (147 in total), point out that most articles about this theme were published in the last five years. These numbers corroborate and highlight the scientific and academic importance of the subject from the perspective of academia and society.

During the review, it was found that most research was focused on weather-based models, which are undoubtedly the most common due to several factors such as relevance and available datasets. It can be stated that these models are used to ascertain the relation of climate on the grapevine to specific situations, on distinct spatial and temporal scales.

Figure 6. Quantity of published articles on the theme in the last 20 years (2004-2024), on the database explored.

It was also identified that most of the work focuses on very specific use cases, performed at distinct application locations and time series, which further hinders the capacity for interoperability of data and outputs, effectively diminishing the impact of the efforts made by the researchers.

The most common topics found were the following (in no specific order):

- Disease dynamics and management (mainly mildew), with a few focused on pest dynamics (*L. Botrana*);
- Yield prediction;
- Physiology;
- Grape berry and vine metabolomics characterization;
- Genomics and genotyping;
- Development, optimization, validation and review of methodologies, predictors, bioclimatic indices, parameters, variables and models;
- Field mapping, site selection, cultivar suitability;
- Soil practices and erosion, operations management / cultural practices;

- Agroecomics and financial analysis;
- Sensor, vehicle and satellite data.

While the list above represents a wide range of topics, most of them make use of common metrics like temperature and precipitation.

Particularly for vineyard modelling, few articles mention the use of ML techniques in crop modelling, since it is still a rare occurrence, being therefore subject to improvement with these tools in the future.

Due to the extensive and widespread development of literature across many use cases and applications, there is a consistent progression observed in most instances. The literature provides evidence that there is a trend towards using model ensembles in crop modelling. Researchers typically transition to model ensembles after dedicating years to developing specialized models to address specific difficulties. This is because ensembles that include different models often bear the potential to produce better results, albeit being considered more complex (Fraga and Malheiro, 2013; Wallach *et al.*, 2016; Martre *et al.*, 2015).

State of the art

Agricultural systems are interconnected with various environmental elements, including species, ecosystems, and human activities. Agricultural crops are not isolated systems in the real world, and their study involves permanent connections with other species, ecosystem elements, like soil, hydric resources, and sunlight, and human activities, directly or indirectly (Bhandari *et al.*, 2024).

Several authors (Fraga *et al.*, 2016a; Mosedale *et al.*, 2015; Ollat *et al.*, 2017; Santos *et al.*, 2020b) have investigated the complex problem of climate change for several years and concluded that in order to achieve sustainable grape and wine production, it is necessary to address extreme weather events, and promote the use of multidisciplinary studies and new scientific approaches to address the impact of climate change on viticulture, such as crop modelling.

Crop modelling, as a field of study, belongs to the agricultural systems science, which in turn is an interdisciplinary field that studies complex agricultural systems, involving components, and interactions in the plant-climate-environment nexus as well as human factors. It can enhance agricultural productivity by providing insights from data and aiding in decision-making (Saxena and Armstrong 2014; Jones *et al.*, 2017; Nowak 2021; Nti *et al.*, 2023; Crespo *et al.*, 2024).

Crop modelling inputs are crucial for accurately simulating plant growth and yield, particularly in viticulture, where specific environmental and management factors significantly influence outcomes. Key inputs include soil properties, such as texture, moisture content and nutrient availability, which directly affect root development and water uptake. Additionally, climatic data—encompassing temperature, precipitation, and solar radiation—are vital for understanding how weather patterns impact grapevine phenology and growth stages. For instance, growing degree days (GDD) are often used to quantify heat accumulation, which is crucial for predicting flowering and ripening times in

grapevines (Fraga *et al.*, 2016b; Malheiro *et al.*, 2013).

The origins of crop simulation modelling can be traced back to the 1960s when the first mathematical relationships between biomass growth and solar radiation were established (Asseng *et al.*, 2014). Since then, crop models have been applied to a diversified range of end uses, focusing on understanding and predicting various factors such as yield, climate change, water status, nutrient intake, and disease occurrence. These models have played a crucial role in evaluating the potential effects of climate change on cropping systems and in exploring adaptation strategies to mitigate its impacts. By combining historical data with seasonal predictions, there has been significant development over the years and is now recognized as an essential tool in agriculture, particularly in viticulture (Boote *et al.*, 1996; Asseng *et al.*, 2014; Saxena and Armstrong, 2014; Jones *et al.*, 2017; Khaki and Wang, 2019; Nowak, 2021; Nti *et al.*, 2023; Xiao and Shi, 2023).

Within crop models, two predominant approaches emerge: dynamic and statistical. While both seek to unravel the underlying patterns and structures of crops, the methodologies and focuses vary considerably (Fraga *et al.*, 2016a; Jones *et al.*, 2017). Statistical models are static in nature, portraying the crop as a static and immutable entity at a given point in time. They are based on the historical statistical relationship between crop parameters such as yield, air temperature and other environmental factors. These models provide relationships at a given moment, though may fail to capture the dynamics and temporal evolution (Ahmed *et al.*, 2022). Statistical models are also known as empirical models. On the other hand, dynamic models recognize the fluid and constantly evolving nature of crops. Dynamic crop models, provide explainable perceptions of the physiological processes in response to varying conditions, integrating species, varietal characteristics, local weather, soil types, and management options. These models are also known as mechanistic or process-based models.

Both types of models are becoming important decision-support systems for monitoring crops. They are used to understand cultural changes over time, considering a variety of factors. The early forecasting of parameters such as phenology, water status, yield and potential wine characteristics has stood out for its crucial usefulness in the wine sector (Saxena and Armstrong, 2014; Jones *et al.*, 2017; Wallach *et al.*, 2019; Nowak, 2021; Katzin *et al.*, 2022; Nti *et al.*, 2023). However, these models exhibit limitations in terms of processing large amounts of data, computational requirements, simplification of results, and individual calibration for each grape variety and location, due to these regional particularities such as climatic, edaphic and topographic (Fraga *et al.*, 2015; Fraga *et al.*, 2016a). This issue is intensified in Portuguese winegrowing regions, which have distinct climatic, soil, and topographic characteristics, affecting crop growth and development, requiring a case-by-case calibration for each grapevine variety and location (Fraga *et al.*, 2015; Fraga *et al.*, 2016b). Multi-scale phenomics presents a challenge for modelling (Tardieu *et al.*, 2017), and, due to historical barriers like technical requirements and perceived credibility, have not fully transitioned from research to real-world operations (Knowling *et al.*, 2021).

The performance of dynamic crop models is intrinsically linked to the quality of the used data, emphasizing the necessity for robust phenological databases to ensure accurate predictions. By integrating high-quality phenological data into these models, researchers can achieve better calibration and, consequently, more precise forecasts of crop growth dynamics. This is particularly important in regions with diverse climatic and edaphic conditions, such as those found in Portuguese viticulture, where tailored modelling approaches are required to account for local variations. Thus, advancing the field of phenological modelling is vital for enhancing the efficacy of dynamic crop models, ultimately leading to improved agricultural decision-making and management practices (Costa *et al.*, 2015).

Phenology is defined as the study of the relation between climate and periodic biological phenomena, either in plants or animals. The prediction of phenological events, such as budbreak, flowering, véraison (Messina *et al.*, 2020; Piña-Rey *et al.*, 2021), can provide valuable insights into the effects of climate change on grapevines (Hall and Blackman, 2019), and are frequently used in viticultural research to study climate change impacts. Research on phenological models considers various shapes of response functions and input data resolution, with sub-daily temperatures and responses becoming more prominent in grapevine phenology modelling. The accuracy of these models typically allows to predict major stages within ± 7 days (Ruml *et al.*, 2016; Parker *et al.*, 2020; Ruml and Korać 2020; Schmidt *et al.*, 2022).

Phenology models are divided into three types: analytical, statistical, and mechanistic. Analytical models focus on optimizing resource acquisition by understanding leaf lifespan strategies. Statistical models relate phenological events to climatic factors and use statistical fitting methods to estimate parameters. Some models are more mechanistic, involving simple correlations with average temperature or more complex ones like the Spring Indices Models. Mechanistic models describe cause-effect relationships between physiological processes and environmental factors, with parameters typically based on systems theory rather than statistical inference (Chuine *et al.*, 2013).

In viticulture, phenological modelling is crucial for understanding the timing of grapevine developmental stages, which are significantly influenced by climatic conditions. The primary inputs for these models normally include temperature data, which is often quantified using GDD and other thermal time indices. GDD is calculated as the cumulative sum of daily mean temperatures above a specified base temperature, which is essential for predicting key phenological (Costa *et al.*, 2019; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2022).

Accurate phenological modelling is essential for vineyard management decisions, as the timing of these developmental stages can

significantly influence field operations and consequently impact grape yield and quality (Verdugo-Vásquez *et al.*, 2016; Leolini *et al.*, 2020). By developing robust phenological models tailored to specific grapevine cultivars and regions, researchers can provide valuable insights for grape growers to optimize their cultivation practices and mitigate risks associated with climate variability (Mosedale *et al.*, 2016).

In the present state, models are very reliant on input data quality to produce good results. This occurs to such an extent that some authors claim that the quality of the results can almost be predicted to be approximately the same level as the quality of the input directly influencing the effectiveness and validity of the model's outputs. (Pasley *et al.*, 2023). Although modelling is an iterative process with frequent updates and enhancements, the application of statistics and ML can facilitate the calibration of model parameters, potentially leading to more efficient model improvements over time (Fraga *et al.*, 2024).

Artificial intelligence (AI) has significantly impacted the viticulture industry by providing access to more data and information. ML algorithms are used in precision viticulture, with two categories: supervised learning and unsupervised learning.

Supervised learning uses labeled data to train models to predict outcomes accurately, while unsupervised learning works with unlabeled data to discover hidden patterns and relationships. Deep learning is a subset of supervised ML that uses artificial neural networks with multiple layers to analyze complex agricultural data (Tripathi *et al.*, 2022).

Ferro and Catania (2023) highlight that regression analysis is a frequently used ML technique, which demonstrated high accuracy in predicting vineyard yields and classification tasks, vineyard component classification, weed detection, disease detection, and grape quality. ML models have been used to accurately forecast grape sugar levels, as well as for the purpose of segmenting and classifying vineyards to enhance vineyard management. The authors also state that deep

learning algorithms are commonly employed for object detection in precision viticulture, particularly in identifying and differentiating signs of certain vine diseases, while also enabling improved predictions and decision-making in crop management. However, some drawbacks to this novel approach have been identified, such as reliance on accurate data collection and input (using multiple datasets from various sources is laborious) and limitations due to data quality and representativeness (Hussein *et al.*, 2024). Additional considerations include the practical implementation of these methods, which necessitates significant initial investments in technology acquisition and personnel training. There are limitations due to data quality and representativeness, demanding specialized equipment and human resources, for results interpretation with technical expertise and cultural knowledge, often requiring collaboration between academia and practitioners (Araújo *et al.*, 2023).

Conversely, ML models treat crop yield as an implicit function of input variables, which can be highly non-linear and complex, thus allowing for comprehensive analysis of agricultural data (Biddappa *et al.*, 2024). The main potential uses of ML in crop modelling include enhanced crop yield prediction, precise soil monitoring, improved suitability analysis, increased productivity, reduced production costs, improved crop quality, and efficient resource management. ML can also identify emerging cultural trends and predict future changes (Seng *et al.*, 2018; Zhou *et al.*, 2021; Zhao *et al.*, 2023; Elufioye *et al.*, 2024).

Nowadays, most modern vineyards employ sensors and platforms to identify spatial variations, with particular emphasis on the use of multispectral sensors, hyperspectral sensors, visual sensors, thermal sensors, and laser altimetry. These sensors are employed for monitoring vegetative growth, estimating yield, controlling diseases, mapping nutrition, and monitoring water status. The advancement of Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV) platforms has the potential to streamline cultivation operations and enhance their effectiveness. This includes tasks like weed

control, soil tillage, harvesting, and plant protection (Kontogiannis *et al.*, 2024).

The opportunities and challenges identified in this review are summarized in Table I.

Table I

Opportunities and challenges identified in the review

Opportunities	Challenges
1. Enhanced agricultural productivity through data-driven insights	1. Complexity of agricultural systems and their interconnections
2. Improved decision-making in vineyard management	2. Need for high-quality, comprehensive datasets
3. Better understanding of climate change impacts on viticulture	3. Computational requirements for processing large amounts of data
4. More accurate predictions of phenological stages	4. Simplification of results, potentially losing nuanced information
5. Optimization of resource management (water, nutrients, etc.)	5. Individual calibration required for each grape variety and location
6. Early detection and management of diseases and pests	6. Addressing multi-scale phenomics in modelling
7. Precise yield predictions	7. Transitioning from research to real-world operations
8. Improved grape quality assessment	8. Initial investment in technology and training
9. Efficient field mapping and site selection	9. Interpretation of complex model outputs
10. Advanced soil monitoring and management	10. Integration of traditional knowledge with new technologies
11. Integration of multidisciplinary approaches in viticulture research	11. Balancing model complexity with practical applicability
12. Development of cultivar-specific and region-specific models	12. Addressing the unique climatic, edaphic, and topographic conditions of specific regions
13. Streamlined cultivation operations using Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGVs)	13. Ensuring model adaptability to changing climate conditions
	14. Overcoming historical barriers and perceived credibility issues

The history of agricultural systems modelling reveals key lessons for future development. The integration of technological advances, open data, transdisciplinary collaboration, modularity, and user-driven data in developing next-generation agricultural system models is crucial for efficient scientific progress and model longevity, requiring a more concentrated effort to connect several modelling, database, and decision support systems at distinct scales. Essentially, the next generation of models requires major advances in agricultural systems science, considering all challenges and avoiding re-invention (Jones *et al.*, 2017).

Cola *et al.* (2014) explored the plant-environment-climate nexus using model ensembles, emphasizing the importance of holistic viticulture approaches. The complex connections within agricultural systems are crucial for understanding the holistic nature of

the industry and the implications of interventions or assessments, as any assessment that disregards these connections will be incomplete and uncertain (Salazar-Rojas *et al.*, 2023).

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This review highlights the integration of crop modelling and ML techniques in Portuguese viticulture, emphasizing their importance in addressing the challenges posed by climate change and regional variability.

The findings indicate a significant increase in research focused on ML applications in viticulture, covering various topics such as disease management, yield prediction, and field mapping.

Phenological modelling is crucial for understanding grapevine developmental

stages, and the advancement of dynamic crop models, supported by robust databases, enhances prediction accuracy for key viticultural events. Recent advancements (Fraga *et al.*, 2024) in ML applied to crop models for the Portuguese vineyards, underscore the necessity for tailored crop models that reflect the unique climatic, edaphic, and topographic conditions of Portuguese winegrowing regions. While ML offers substantial benefits, including improved yield predictions and resource management, challenges, such as data quality and the need for specialized expertise, remain.

Ultimately, overcoming these challenges can significantly enhance the efficiency, productivity, resilience, and sustainability of the Portuguese wine industry. The future of viticulture will depend on the effective integration of advanced modelling techniques with traditional practices to ensure adaptability in an uncertain environment.

In conclusion, future viticulture scenarios will involve models, Internet of Things (IoT), and interconnected technologies such as satellites and sensors for real-time data transfer and processing, as researchers' efforts consider directly real-world scenarios, bridging theoretical and practical gaps, and promoting interdisciplinary collaboration.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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REFERENCES

- Ahmed Z., Gui D., Qi Z., Liu Y., Liu Y., Azmat M., 2022. Agricultural system modeling: current achievements, innovations, and future roadmap. *Arab. J. Geosci.*, **15**.
- Alibabaei K., Assunção E., Gaspar P. D., Soares V. N. G. J., Caldeira J. M. L. P., 2022. Real-Time Detection of Vine Trunk for Robot Localization Using Deep Learning Models Developed for Edge TPU Devices. *Future Internet*, **14**, 199.
- Antle J. M., Jones J. W., Rosenzweig C., 2017. Next generation agricultural system models and knowledge products: Synthesis and strategy. *Agric. Syst.*, **155**, 179–185.
- Araújo S. O., Peres R. S., Ramalho J. C., Lidon F., Barata J., 2023. Machine Learning Applications in Agriculture: Current Trends, Challenges, and Future Perspectives. *Agron.*, **13**.
- Asseng S., Zhu Y., Basso B., Wilson T., Cammarano D., 2014. Simulation Modeling: Applications in Cropping Systems. In *Encyclopedia of Agriculture and Food Systems*, 102–112. Elsevier.
- Bhandari S., Bishnu, Y., Kumar Y. P., Vivek L., Sudip K., 2024. 'Exploring Agroecological Approaches for Sustainable Agriculture and Rural Development: A Comprehensive Review'. *Asian J. Res. Agric. For.* **10**, 79–90.
- Biasi R., Brunori E., Ferrara C., Salvati L., 2019. Assessing Impacts of Climate Change on Phenology and Quality Traits of *Vitis vinifera* L.: The Contribution of Local Knowledge. *Plants* **8**.
- Biddappa C. B., V Dr. S., 2024. Crop Yield Prediction on Agriculture Using Machine Learning. *Inter. J. Res. Pub. Rev.*, **5**, 165–167.
- Boote K. J., Jones J. W., Pickering N. B., 1996. Potential Uses and Limitations of Crop Models. *Agron. J.*, **88**, 704–716.
- Bucur G. M., Dejeu L., 2022. Research on Adaptation Measures of Viticulture to Climate Change: Overview. *Scientific Papers. Series B, Horticulture*, **LXVI**, 177–190.
- Chuine I., Cortazar-Atauri I. G. de, Kramer K., Hänninen H., 2013. Plant Development Models. In *Phenology an Integrative environmental science*, 275–278. Springer, Dordrecht.
- Cola G., Mariani L., Salinari F., Civardi S., Bernizzoni F., Gatti M., Poni S., 2014. Description and testing of a weather-based model for predicting phenology, canopy development and source-sink balance in *Vitis vinifera* L. cv. Barbera. *Agric. For. Meteorol.*, **184**, 117–136.
- Costa R., Fraga H., Fonseca A., Cortázar-Atauri I. G. De, Val M. C., Carlos C., Reis S., Santos J. A., 2019. Grapevine Phenology of cv. Touriga Franca and Touriga Nacional in the Douro Wine Region: Modelling and Climate Change Projections. *Agron.*, **9**.
- Costa R., Fraga H., Malheiro A. C., Santos J. A., 2015. Application of crop modelling to portuguese viticulture: Implementation and added-values for strategic planning. *Ciênc. Téc. Vitivinícola*, **30**, 29–42.
- Crespo N., Pádua L., Santos J. A., Fraga H., 2024. Satellite Remote Sensing Tools for Drought Assessment in Vineyards and Olive Orchards: A Systematic Review. *Remote Sens.*, **16**, 2040.

- Ding Y., Wang L., Li Y., Li D., 2018. Model predictive control and its application in agriculture: A review. *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, **151**, 104–117.
- Duarte J. B., Brinca P., Gonçalves M. J., 2022. Setor do Vinho - Avaliação de impacto socioeconómico em Portugal.
- Elufioye O. A., Chinedu U.I., Olubusola O, Favour O.U., Noluthando Z.M., 2024. Ai-Driven Predictive Analytics in Agricultural Supply Chains: A Review: Assessing the Benefits and Challenges of Ai in Forecasting Demand and Optimizing Supply in Agriculture. *Comput. Sci. IT Res. J.*, **5**, 473–497.
- FAOSTAT, 2020. The State of Food and Agriculture 2020 Overcoming water challenges in agriculture. Rome
- FAOSTAT, 2023. Land statistics 2001-2022 Global, regional and country trends.
- Ferreira C. S. S., Veiga A., Caetano A., Gonzalez-Pelayo O., Karine-Boulet A., Abrantes N., Keizer J., Ferreira A. J. D., 2020. Assessment of the Impact of Distinct Vineyard Management Practices on Soil Physico-Chemical Properties. *Air, Soil and Water Res.*, **13**.
- Ferro M. V., Catania P., 2023. Technologies and Innovative Methods for Precision Viticulture: A Comprehensive Review. *Horticulturae*, **9**, 399.
- Fraga H., Cortázar Atauri I. G. de, Malheiro A. C., Moutinho-Pereira J., Santos J. A., 2017. Viticulture in Portugal: A review of recent trends and climate change projections. *OENO One*, **51**, 61.
- Fraga H., Costa R., Moutinho-Pereira J., Correia C. M., Dinis L. T., Gonçalves I., Silvestre J., Eiras-Dias J., Malheiro A. C., Santos J. A., 2015. Modeling phenology, water status, and yield components of three Portuguese grapevines using the STICS crop model. *Am. J. Enol. Vitic.*, **66**, 482–491.
- Fraga H., Freitas T. R., Moriondo M., Molitor D., Santos J. A., 2024. Determining the Climatic Drivers for Wine Production in the Cõa Region (Portugal) Using a Machine Learning Approach. *Land*, **13**, 749.
- Fraga H., García de Cortázar Atauri I., Malheiro A. C., Santos J. A., 2016a. Modelling climate change impacts on viticultural yield, phenology and stress conditions in Europe. *Glob. Chang. Biol.*, **22**, 3774–3788.
- Fraga H., Malheiro A. C., 2013. Future scenarios for viticultural zoning in Europe: ensemble projections and uncertainties. *Inter. J. Biometeorol.*, **57**, 909–925.
- Fraga H., Malheiro A. C., Moutinho-Pereira J., Santos J. A., 2012. An overview of climate change impacts on European viticulture. *Food Energy Secur.*, **1**, 94–110.
- Fraga H., Santos J. A., Moutinho-Pereira J., Carlos C., Silvestre J., Eiras-Dias J., Mota T., Malheiro A. C., 2016b. Statistical modelling of grapevine phenology in Portuguese wine regions: observed trends and climate change projections. *J. Agric. Sci.*, **154**, 795–811.
- Gil E., 2021. Vítivinicultura e Mudanças Climáticas: Um estudo sobre as Regiões do Alentejo e Vinhos Verdes sob a ótica da sustentabilidade. Faculdade de Economia da Universidade do Porto, Porto.
- Hall A., Blackman J., 2019. Modelling within-region spatiotemporal variability in grapevine phenology with high resolution temperature data. *OENO One*, **53**, 147–159.
- Hansen J., Ruedy R., Sato M., Lo K., 2020. World of Change: Global Temperatures. *Rev. Geophys.*, **48**.
- Hussein A. H. A., Jabbar K. A., Mohammed A., Jasim L., 2024. Harvesting the Future: AI and IoT in Agriculture. *E3S Web of Conferences*, **477**.
- Jones J. W., Antle J. M., Basso B., Boote K. J., Conant R. T., Foster I., Godfray H. C. J., 2017. Brief history of agricultural systems modeling. *Agric. Syst.*, **155**, 240–254.
- Kamilaris A., Prenafeta-Boldú F. X., 2018. Deep learning in agriculture: A survey. *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, **147**, 70–90.
- Kasimati A., Espejo-Garcia B., Vali E., Malounas I., Fountas S., 2021. Investigating a Selection of Methods for the Prediction of Total Soluble Solids Among Wine Grape Quality Characteristics Using Normalized Difference Vegetation Index Data From Proximal and Remote Sensing. *Front. Plant. Sci.*, **12**, 683078.
- Katzin D., Henten E. J. van, Mourik S. van, 2022. Process-based greenhouse climate models: Genealogy, current status, and future directions. *Agric. Syst.*, **198**, 103388.
- Khaki S., Wang L., 2019. Crop yield prediction using deep neural networks. *Front. Plant. Sci.*, **10**, 452963.
- Knowing M. J., Bennett B., Ostendorf B., Westra S., Walker R. R., Pellegrino A., Edwards E. J., Collins C., Pagay V., Grigg D., 2021. Bridging the gap between data and decisions: A review of process-based models for viticulture. *Agric. Syst.*, **193**, 103209.
- Kontogiannis S., Koundouras S., Pikridas C., 2024. Proposed Fuzzy-Stranded-Neural Network Model That Utilizes IoT Plant-Level Sensory Monitoring and Distributed Services for the Early Detection of Downy Mildew in Viticulture. *Computers*, **13**.
- Kovács E., Puskás J., Pozsgai A., Kozma K., 2018. Shift in the annual growth cycle of grapevines (*Vitis vinifera* L.) in West Hungary. *Appl. Ecol. Environ. Res.*, **16**, 2029–2042.
- Leolini L., Costafreda-Aumedes S., Santos J. A., Menz C., Fraga H., Molitor D., Merante P., 2020. Phenological Model Intercomparison for Estimating Grapevine Budbreak Date (*Vitis vinifera* L.) in Europe. *Appl. Sci.*, **10**, 3800.
- Liakos K. G., Busato P., Moshou D., Pearson S., Bochtis D., 2018. Machine Learning in Agriculture: A Review. *Sensors*, **18**, 2674.
- Malheiro A. C., Campos R., Fraga H., Eiras-Dias J., Silvestre J., Santos J. A., 2013. Winegrape phenology and temperature relationships in the Lisbon wine region, Portugal. *OENO One*, **47**, 287–299.
- Martre P., Wallach D., Asseng S., Ewert F., Jones J. W., Rötter R. P., Boote K. J., 2015. Multimodel ensembles of wheat growth: many models are better than one. *Glob. Chang. Biol.*, **21**, 911–925.
- Messina C. D., Cooper M., Reynolds M., Hammer G. L., 2020. Crop science: A foundation for advancing predictive agriculture. *Crop Sci.*, **60**, 544–546.
- Mosedale J. R., Abernethy K. E., Smart R. E., Wilson R. J., Maclean I. M. D., 2016. Climate change impacts and adaptive strategies: lessons from the grapevine. *Glob. Chang. Biol.*, **22**, 3814–3828.
- Mosedale J. R., Wilson R. J., Maclean I. M. D., 2015. Climate Change and Crop Exposure to Adverse Weather: Changes to Frost Risk and Grapevine Flowering Conditions. *PLoS One*, **10**.
- Nesbitt A., Dorling S., Jones R., Smith D. K. E., Krumins M., Gannon K. E., Dorling L., Johnson Z., Conway D., 2022. Climate change projections for UK viticulture to 2040: a focus on improving suitability for Pinot noir. *OENO One*, **56**, 69–87.

- Nowak B., 2021. Precision Agriculture: Where do We Stand? A Review of the Adoption of Precision Agriculture Technologies on Field Crops Farms in Developed Countries. *Agri. Res.*, **10**, 515–522.
- Nti I. K., Zaman A., Nyarko-Boateng O., Adekoya A. F., Keyeremeh F., 2023. A predictive analytics model for crop suitability and productivity with tree-based ensemble learning. *Dec. Anal. J.*, **8**, 100311.
- OIV, 2024. State of the World Vine and Wine Sector in 2023.
- Ollat N., Leeuwen C. van, Cortazar-Atauri I. G. de, Touzard J.-M., 2017. The challenging issue of climate change for sustainable grape and wine production. *OENO One*, **51**, 59–60.
- Parker A. K., Cortázar-Atauri I. G. de, Trought M. C. T., Destrac A., Agnew R., Sturman A., Leeuwen C. van, 2020. Adaptation to climate change by determining grapevine cultivar differences using temperature-based phenology models. *OENO One*, **54**, 955–974.
- Pasley H., Brown H., Holzworth D., Whish J., Bell L., Huth N., 2023. How to build a crop model. A review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.*, **43**, 1–12.
- Piña-Rey A., Ribeiro H., Fernández-González M., Abreu I., Javier Rodríguez-Rajo F., 2021. Phenological Model to Predict Budbreak and Flowering Dates of Four Vitis vinifera L. Cultivars Cultivated in DO. Ribeiro (North-West Spain). *Plants*, **10**, 502.
- Rességuier L. de, Mary S., Roux R. Le, Petitjean T., Quéno H., Leeuwen C. van, 2020. Temperature Variability at Local Scale in the Bordeaux Area. Relations With Environmental Factors and Impact on Vine Phenology. *Front. Plant. Sci.*, **11**, 521085.
- Rodrigues P., Pedroso V., Reis S., Yang C., Santos J. A., 2022. Climate change impacts on phenology and ripening of cv. Touriga Nacional in the Dão wine region, Portugal. *Inter. J. Climatol.*, **42**, 7117–7132.
- Rossum G. van, 2007. Python Programming Language, in USENIX Annual Technical Conference, California.
- Ruml M., Korać N., 2020. Phenological Models for Predicting the Budburst and Flowering Date of Grapevine. *Агрознање*, **21**.
- Ruml M., Korac N., Vujadinovic M., Vukovic A., Ivanišević D., 2016. Response of grapevine phenology to recent temperature change and variability in the wine-producing area of Sremski Karlovci, Serbia. *J. Agric. Sci.*, **154**, 186–206.
- Salazar-Rojas A., Castro-Huerta R., Altieri M., 2023. The main agroecological structure, a methodology for the collective analysis of the Mediterranean agroecological landscape of San Clemente, Region del Maule, Chile. *Front. Sustain. Food. Syst.*, **7**, 1241648.
- Santos J. A., Fraga H., Malheiro A. C., Moutinho-Pereira J., Dinis L. T., Correia C., Moriondo M., 2020a. A Review of the Potential Climate Change Impacts and Adaptation Options for European Viticulture. *Appl. Sci.*, **10**, 3092.
- Santos M., Fonseca A., Fraga H., Jones G. V., Santos J. A., 2020b. Bioclimatic conditions of the Portuguese wine denominations of origin under changing climates. *Inter. J. Climatol.*, **40**, 927–941.
- Saxena L., Armstrong L., 2014. A survey of image processing techniques for agriculture. *Research outputs 2014 to 2021*.
- Schmidt D., Kahlen K., Bahr C., Friedel M., 2022. Towards a Stochastic Model to Simulate Grapevine Architecture: A Case Study on Digitized Riesling Vines Considering Effects of Elevated CO₂. *Plants*, **11**, 801.
- Seng K. P., Ang L. M., Schmidtke L. M., Rogiers S. Y., 2018. Computer vision and machine learning for viticulture technology. *IEEE Access*, **6**, 67494–67510.
- Sirník I., Quéno H., Jiménez-Bello M. Á., Manzano J., Roux R. Le, 2018. Viticulture under climate change impact: future climate and irrigation modelling. *E3S Web of Conferences*, **50**, 01041.
- Tardieu F., Cabrera-Bosquet L., Pridmore T., Bennett M., 2017. Plant Phenomics, From Sensors to Knowledge. *Curr. Biol.*, **27**, 770–783.
- Tripathi P., Kumar N., Rai M., Khan A., 2022. Applications of Deep Learning in Agriculture. In Artificial Intelligence Applications in Agriculture and Food Quality Improvement. IGI Global. 17–28.
- United Nations, 2024. World Population Prospects.
- Venios X., Korkas E., Nisiotou A., Banilas G., 2020. Grapevine Responses to Heat Stress and Global Warming. *Plants*, **9**, 1–15.
- Verdugo-Vásquez N., Acevedo-Opazo C., Valdés-Gómez H., Araya-Alman M., Ingram B., García de Cortázar-Atauri I., Tisseyre B., 2016. Spatial variability of phenology in two irrigated grapevine cultivar growing under semi-arid conditions. *Precis. Agric.*, **17**, 218–245.
- Wallach D., Makowski D., Jones J. W., Brun F., 2019. Working with Dynamic Crop Models Methods, Tools and Examples for Agriculture and Environment. Academic Press.
- Wallach D., Mearns L. O., Ruane A. C., Rötter R. P., Asseng S., 2016. Lessons from climate modeling on the design and use of ensembles for crop modeling. *Clim. Change*, **139**, 551–564.
- Webster J., Watson R. T., 2002. Analyzing the Past to Prepare for the Future: Writing a Literature Review. *MIS Quarterly*, **26**, iii–xiii.
- Xiao D., Shi W., 2023. Modeling the Adaptation of Agricultural Production to Climate Change. *Agri.*, **13**, 414.
- Zhao W., Wang M., Pham V. T., 2023. Unmanned Aerial Vehicle and Geospatial Analysis in Smart Irrigation and Crop Monitoring on IoT Platform. *Mob. Info. Sys.*, **2023**.
- Zhou X., Kono Y., Win A., Matsui T., Tanaka T. S. T., 2021. Predicting within-field variability in grain yield and protein content of winter wheat using UAV-based multispectral imagery and machine learning approaches. *Plant Prod. Sci.*, **24**, 137–151.